

Eurodoc Statement on the Swedish Government's decision on cutting the funding for development research

On June 22 2023, the Swedish Government made an amendment to the regulatory letter of the Swedish Research Council. This amendment terminated the longstanding funding program for development research in Sweden effective immediately. This program, notabene, was renewed last summer and was supposed to run at least until 2028¹.

While research projects that have already received funding through this program will not be affected, the current review process has been terminated, with this year's applicants having received the information that their application will not be reviewed and thus has been rejected². As the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions (SUHF)³ and the Nordic Young Academies⁴ Eurodoc deems the decision and the precedence this sets to be highly problematic, particularly for how it affects both academic freedom as well as the academic future of early career researchers.

First, the decision taken by the Government clearly interferes with a politically independent determination of which research topics receive funding, thus threatening both researchers' and institutions' academic freedom. It also undermines the trust researchers, academic institutions, and society can have in that the decision about funding of research topics is not politically controlled by changing governments. In a democratic society, we need critical, free, and politically independent academic research, also for fields that changing governments across the political spectrum might not deem relevant or important. The decision of what kind of research receives funding must not be at the whim of party politics.

While we recognise that the size and scope of publicly funded research is subject to larger political changes, we wish to stress the importance that political influence does not interfere directly with decisions of which research receives funding. With the closing of an entire research program, this is clearly not the case: We just witnessed the politically motivated cutting of a specific type of research program overnight. It is a shock to individual researchers as well as the entire research environment.

Sweden has a long-standing history as a leading country for research on poverty reduction and sustainability. Already earlier in its mandate, the Swedish government has cut the funding of its program aimed at the education of researchers in the Global South by 54%⁵. It is thus to be seen how the entire Swedish research environment will be affected by now also cutting this specific funding program for development research.

Second, launching a call for research projects on which researchers spend large amounts of time and efforts to apply, and to retrospectively change rules or even terminate the funding

¹ [Strategi för Sveriges utvecklingssamarbete inom forskning för fattigdomsbekämpning och hållbar utveckling](#)

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<https://www.vr.se/english/just-now/news/news-archive/2023-06-27-no-new-grants-in-development-research.html>

³ [The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions \(SUHF\): Skrivelse till regeringen från SUHF angående utvecklingsforskning](#)

⁴ [The Nordic Young Academies express profound concern regarding the current state of Nordic Research Policies](#)

⁵ <https://www.omvarlden.se/nyheter/700-farre-forskare-da-bistandet-minskar>

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program, is an unacceptable practice. This is particularly damaging for early career researchers (ECRs), as ECRs more often are not permanently employed and thus rely to a larger extent than the rest of the research community on competitive project funding. Such a terminated call not only voids their work but also diminishes the likelihood of their chances to prolong their employment and career in academia. To emphasise: This practice actively endangers the careers particularly of ECRs. Fundamentally, researchers must be able to trust that by the time of application, the public funding they are applying for is a reliable source of funding, subject to the previously published process of competitive selection.

In conclusion, the Swedish government's decision harms the entire academic system and sets a dangerous precedent that Eurodoc condemns both for its disregard of academic freedom, as well as for the harm done to the career of ECRs.

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Date of Publication: 07.07.2023

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 25 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 23 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research and innovation in Europe.

